

Genome assemblies of the blast fungus *Magnaporthe* (Syn. *Pyricularia*) spp. collected from wild grasses in Germany

A. Cristina Barragan¹, Joe Win¹, Adeline Harant¹, Sophien Kamoun^{1*} and Thorsten Langner^{1*}

¹The Sainsbury Laboratory, University of East Anglia, Norwich Research Park, Norwich, UK

²Centre for Life's Origins and Evolution, Department of Genetics, Evolution and Environment, University College London, UK

*Corresponding authors

E-mail: sophien.kamoun@tsl.ac.uk (SK), thorsten.langner@tsl.ac.uk (TL)

We report long-range sequencing of four blast fungus *Magnaporthe* (Syn. *Pyricularia*) spp. isolates collected from south-western Germany in August of 2021. Two of the isolates were collected from infected host plants foxtail millet (*Setaria* spp.) while the other two from crabgrass (*Digitaria* spp.). We acquired high quality assemblies through a combination of long read sequencing using Oxford Nanopore Technology and subsequent polishing with Illumina short reads. We provide these open access genome assemblies as an open science resource as part of the [OpenWheatBlast](#) and [OpenRiceBlast](#) initiatives.

Introduction

Genomics assisted surveillance is critical to assess distribution and spread of plant pathogens and to develop disease management strategies. Climatic conditions in Germany have so far been considered unfavorable for the proliferation and spread of the blast fungus ([EPPO](#), 2019), one of the most devastating plant pathogens worldwide (Dean et al. 2012; Fisher et al. 2012). However, in August 2021 we observed disease symptoms consistent with the blast fungus on the wild grasses foxtail millet (*Setaria* spp.) and crabgrass (*Digitaria* spp.) in south-western Germany. Further characterization of colony, spore and appressorium morphology of these samples in the laboratory were consistent with blast disease. Our aim was to genetically characterize these isolates and confirm the blast fungus is present in Germany. To achieve this goal, we selected four blast fungus German isolates for whole genome sequencing using Oxford Nanopore and Illumina technologies.

Results

We whole-genome sequenced two representative single spore isolates infecting *Setaria* spp. (isolate ID GE12B and GE10A2) and two infecting *Digitaria* spp. (isolate ID GE3 and GE16_2) using the PromethION sequencing platform. Long-read sequencing of these four samples resulted in a

mean read length of >20kb and read N50 of >30kb (**Table 1**). Next, to improve the quality of the assemblies, we sequenced the same four fungal isolates using Illumina short reads. Assemblies were polished using these short reads through two consecutive iterations of Pilon (v1.23) (Walker et al. 2014). To evaluate the completeness of our assemblies, and track improvements in the genome polishing process, we ran Benchmarking sets of Universal Single-Copy Orthologs (BUSCO) (Simão et al. 2015; Seppey, Manni, and Zdobnov 2019) using the ascomycota_odb10 database (Manni et al. 2021) for each genome assembly. We found that the polishing step improved the BUSCO completeness score of the assemblies from 98.5-98.8% before polishing (**Table 2**) to 98.8-98.9% after polishing (**Table 3**) and reduced the fraction of fragmented BUSCO genes from 0.1-0.2% before polishing (**Table 2**) to 0.1% after polishing (**Table 3**).

Conclusions

The final polished genome assemblies of these four isolates will confirm the presence of the blast fungus in Germany. This will give us useful insights into the geographical distribution of the blast fungus across central Europe and will stress the importance for pathogen surveillance. The achieved number of contigs and total length of the polished genome assemblies, which ranged from 44.3-44.8 Mb, indicate near-complete sequencing of the four fungal isolates. In addition, the high BUSCO completeness score of the polished assemblies indicates that conserved fungal gene orthologs are well represented. Finally, we advocate for open access of genomic data and encourage the community to use this sequencing information to better tackle blast disease across the world.

Materials and Methods

Sample collection and phenotypic pathogen characterization

In mid-August of 2021, we observed blast disease symptoms on hosts wild foxtail millet (*Setaria* spp.) and crabgrass (*Digitaria* spp.) in the state of Rhineland-Palatinate, in south-western Germany (Latitude 49.08314° N, Longitude 8.20417° E). Infected plants showed lesions typical for blast disease. We collected diseased plant material and phenotypically inspected them further in the laboratory. We whole-genome sequenced two representative single spore isolates infecting *Setaria* spp. (isolate ID GE12B and GE10A2) and two infecting *Digitaria* spp. (isolate ID GE3 and GE16_2). For this purpose, we extracted high molecular weight DNA following the protocol described in (Jones et al. 2021). Sequencing runs were performed by Future Genomics Technologies (Leiden, The Netherlands) using the PromethION sequencing platform (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, Oxford, UK). Long reads were assembled into contigs and corrected using Flye (v2.9-b1768) (Kolmogorov et al. 2019), and polished with long reads using Medaka (v1.4.3) (<https://github.com/nanoporetech/medaka>). All assemblies were additionally polished using short read Illumina sequencing technologies (San Diego, USA) through two consecutive iterations of Pilon (v1.23) (Walker et al. 2014).

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Table 1. Summary statistics of PromethION runs for genomic DNA of German *Magnaporthe* isolates

Sample name	Barcode	total # reads	total # data (Mb)	mean read (nt)	read N50 (nt)	ENA Accession ¹
GEI2B	NB03	251,937	5,125	20,343	31,090	ERR9866173
GEI0A2	NB04	248,647	5,793	23,297	34,292	ERR9866254
GE3	NB05	198,641	4,670	23,512	35,801	ERR9883755 , ERR9883756
GEI6_2	NB06	306,395	6,589	21,506	33,327	ERR9866258 , ERR9866259

¹ Sequencing reads were deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) under study accession number PRJEB53658.

Table 2. Summary statistics of unpolished genome assemblies of German *Magnaporthe* isolates

Sample name	Assembly length (bp) ¹	No. contigs	Contig N50 (bp)	Largest contig (bp)	Mean coverage (x fold)	Complete BUSCO ²	Complete & single-copy BUSCOs	Complete & duplicated BUSCOs	Fragmented BUSCOs	Missing BUSCOs
GEI2B	44,312,842	20	5,068,283	8,379,733	109	98.80%	98.70%	0.10%	0.10%	1.10%
GEI0A2	44,788,745	29	6,975,948	11,007,366	123	98.80%	98.60%	0.20%	0.10%	1.10%
GE3	43,475,825	15	5,242,186	8,070,036	105	98.70%	98.60%	0.10%	0.10%	1.20%
GEI6_2	43,698,161	13	6,236,348	8,076,153	146	98.60%	98.50%	0.10%	0.20%	1.20%

¹ Contigs were *de novo* assembled and corrected using Flye vs. 2.9-b1768, polished based on ONT reads using Medaka vs. 1.4.3.

² BUSCO=Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs. BUSCO was run using ascomycota_odb10 dataset (Manni et al. 2021).

Table 3. Summary statistics of polished genome assemblies of German *Magnaporthe* isolates.

Sample name	Assembly length (bp)	No. contigs	Contig N50 (bp)	Largest contig (bp)	Mean coverage (x fold)	Complete BUSCO ¹	Complete & single-copy BUSCOs	Complete & duplicated BUSCOs	Fragmented BUSCOs	Missing BUSCOs	GenBank Accession
GEI2B	44,287,786	20	5,065,357	8,374,180	109	98.90%	98.70%	0.20%	0.10%	1.00%	GCA_944989255.1
GEI0A2	44,757,806	29	6,972,091	11,001,122	123	98.90%	98.70%	0.20%	0.10%	1.00%	GCA_944989335.1
GE3	43,441,267	15	5,238,139	8,063,860	105	98.80%	98.70%	0.10%	0.10%	1.10%	GCA_944989265.1
GEI6_2	43,662,581	13	6,231,040	8,069,839	146	98.80%	98.70%	0.10%	0.10%	1.10%	GCA_944952825.1

¹ BUSCO=Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs. BUSCO was run using ascomycota_odb10 dataset (Manni et al. 2021).